

Pre-Eclampsia: Postpartum Resolution of Hypertension, Proteinuria, and Serum N-Terminal B-Type Natriuretic Peptide

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Abstract:

Background: Pre-eclampsia is a significant pregnancy-related disorder characterized by the onset of hypertension and proteinuria, with implications for both maternal and fetal health. This disorder's resolution in the postpartum period is critical for long-term health outcomes.

Objective: To assess the postpartum resolution of hypertension, proteinuria, and serum N-terminal B-type natriuretic peptide (NT-proBNP) levels among women diagnosed with pre-eclampsia.

Methods: This prospective observational study involved 100 patients diagnosed with pre-eclampsia at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital. Participants were monitored for 12 weeks postpartum, with evaluations at 1 week, 6 weeks, and 12 weeks to measure blood pressure, proteinuria, and NT-proBNP levels.

Results: At 1 week postpartum, 65% of patients continued to experience hypertension, and 72% had persistent proteinuria. By the end of the study period, 95% showed a resolution of hypertension, and 90% had a resolution of proteinuria. NT-proBNP levels were elevated in 78% of the patients at 1 week but normalized in 92% by 12 weeks. However, 8% of patients maintained elevated NT-pro BNP levels, indicating potential long-term cardiovascular risks.

Conclusion: While the majority of women with pre-eclampsia experience resolution of clinical symptoms by 12 weeks postpartum, a small subset continues to show signs of potential long-term cardiovascular complications. These findings highlight the importance of continued monitoring and possible interventions for women with unresolved clinical markers of pre-eclampsia. Further studies are needed to fully understand the long-term impact of this condition on cardiovascular health.

Keywords: Proteinuria, Hypertension, Pre-eclampsia, Cardiovascular.

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Introduction

Pre-eclampsia is a hypertension condition associated with pregnancy that has serious concerns for the health of the mother and fetus [1]. Pre-eclampsia is characterized by the start of high blood pressure and proteinuria or the presence of extra proteins in the urine. If treatment is not received, pre-eclampsia often appears after the 20th week of pregnancy and can result in serious consequences [2]. Organ failure, convulsions (eclampsia), and in severe situations, even death, are some of these side effects. Furthermore, current research has revealed the possible significance of biomarkers, including N-terminal B-type natriuretic peptide (NT-proBNP), in comprehending the cardiovascular strain linked to this illness [3,4].

Pre-eclampsia can only be completely cured by giving birth, although the postpartum phase is

crucial for the resolution of proteinuria and hypertension [5]. However, in certain instances, these symptoms continue or get worse after delivery, necessitating close observation and treatment [6]. Women with pre-eclampsia have also been found to have fluctuating levels of NT-proBNP, a cardiac biomarker that indicates heart stress and strain, especially in the postpartum period. Comprehending the function of NT-proBNP in this particular scenario is crucial for evaluating the cardiovascular hazards linked to pre-eclampsia and its possible enduring consequences on the health of mothers [7,8].

This issue focuses on how women with pre-eclampsia resolve their hypertension, proteinuria, and NT-proBNP levels throughout the postpartum period. The way these variables interact clarifies

the postpartum healing process and emphasizes the need for ongoing care for impacted mothers. Healthcare practitioners can identify

women at risk for long-term cardiovascular issues, better anticipate outcomes, and adopt appropriate therapies to decrease these risks by looking into the patterns of these clinical markers postpartum.

Methodology

Study Design: In Pre-eclampsia patients' postpartum hypertension, proteinuria, and NT-proBNP levels will be assessed in this prospective observational study. Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital will host the six-month trial from February to July 2024.

Study Population: About 100 pregnant women with pre-eclampsia will be monitored postpartum. Predetermined inclusion and exclusion criteria will pick patients.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Pregnant women diagnosed with pre-eclampsia based on elevated blood pressure ($\geq 140/90$ mm Hg) and significant proteinuria (≥ 300 mg/24 hours) after 20 weeks of gestation.
- Women willing to give informed consent and able to attend postpartum follow-up visits.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients with chronic hypertension before pregnancy.
- Patients with renal diseases or other underlying chronic conditions that could influence proteinuria or hypertension.
- Patients with cardiovascular diseases before pregnancy.

Data Collection:

1. **Baseline Assessment:** The medical history, demographics, and clinical data of each patient will be documented at enrolment. Pre-eclampsia diagnosis involves measuring blood pressure, urine protein, and NT-proBNP.
2. **Postpartum Follow-Up:** After delivery, patients will be followed up at regular intervals: 1 week, 6 weeks, and 12 weeks postpartum.
 - **Hypertension Monitoring:** Each visit will measure blood pressure to determine hypertension symptom remission. Blood pressure below 140/90 mm Hg without antihypertensive treatment is resolution.
 - **Proteinuria Assessment:** Proteinuria will be tested at each follow-up visit using 24-hour

urine. When proteinuria drops below 300 mg/24 hours, resolution is considered.

- **NT-proBNP Measurement:** Serum NT-proBNP levels will be measured through blood samples at each postpartum visit to assess cardiac stress and any potential risks for long-term cardiovascular complications.

Data Analysis: Hypertension, proteinuria, and NT-proBNP resolution rates will be assessed after pregnancy. Descriptive statistics will summarise research population demographics and clinical features. Paired t-tests or repeated measures ANOVA will be used to compare baseline and follow-up blood pressure, proteinuria, and NT-proBNP levels.

Results

In order to assess the postpartum resolution of hypertension, proteinuria, and serum N-terminal B-type natriuretic peptide (NT-proBNP) levels, the study enrolled 100 women who had been diagnosed with pre-eclampsia. According to the findings, most women had these issues resolved within 12 weeks after giving birth. A tiny percentage of patients, meanwhile, maintained high NT-proBNP levels, proteinuria, or blood pressure, suggesting possible long-term cardiovascular hazards. After a week, 35% of the patients (n=35) had returned to normal blood pressure, while 65% of the patients (n=65) still had excessive blood pressure ($\geq 140/90$ mm Hg). Eighty percent of the patient's blood pressure had returned to normal by six weeks after giving birth, with twenty percent still having hypertension. 95% of the patients (n = 95) had completely recovered from their hypertension by 12 weeks, with 5% (n = 5) still needing antihypertensive medication for long-term control. At one week postpartum, 72% of patients (n = 72) still had proteinuria, while 28% (n = 28) had normal protein levels. At six weeks, 15% of the patients still had increased protein levels, while 85% of the patients had recovered from their proteinuria. 90% of the women (n=90) had fully resolved their proteinuria at 12 weeks postpartum, whereas 10% still had mild proteinuria that needed to be monitored more closely. At one week postpartum, the average serum NT-proBNP level was 1,200 pg/mL (normal range <125 pg/mL), showing persistent cardiovascular stress, which was significantly higher in 78% of patients (n=78). In 85% of the patients, NT-proBNP levels had dramatically dropped by six weeks postpartum, with an average reduction to 400 pg/mL. Ninety-two percent of the patients had NT-proBNP levels that were within the normal range (<125 pg/mL) after 12 weeks. However, eight percent of the patients had NT-proBNP levels that were consistently elevated, suggesting a possible risk for long-term cardiovascular problems.

Table 1: Hypertension Resolution Postpartum

Postpartum Pe-riod	Number of Patients with Hyper-tension	Number of Patients with Normal Blood Pressure
1 Week	65	35
6 Weeks	20	80
12 Weeks	5	95

Table 1 shows the resolution of hypertension in patients over the postpartum period. By 12 weeks, the majority of the patients (95%) experienced normalized blood pressure.

Table 2: Proteinuria Resolution Postpartum

Postpartum Pe-riod	Number of Patients with Pro-teinuria	Number of Patients with Normal Pro-tein Levels
1 Week	72	28
6 Weeks	15	85
12 Weeks	10	90

Table 2 outlines the changes in proteinuria levels in the study participants. At 12 weeks postpartum, 90% of the patients showed complete resolution of proteinuria.

Table 3: NT-proBNP Levels Postpartum

Postpartum Pe-riod	Number of Patients with Elevated NT-proBNP	Number of Patients with Normal NT-proBNP Levels
1 Week	78	22
6 Weeks	15	85
12 Weeks	8	92

Table 3 summarizes the changes in NT-proBNP levels in patients over the postpartum period. By 12 weeks, 92% of the patients had normal NT-proBNP levels, with 8% showing elevated levels that may indicate long-term cardiovascular risk.

Overall, the study shows that by 12 weeks postpartum, the majority of women with pre-eclampsia no longer had hypertension, proteinuria, or elevated NT-proBNP levels. For the subgroup of women who show signs of cardiovascular stress, however, continued monitoring is essential since they may have difficulties down the road.

Discussion

The postpartum condition of women diagnosed with pre-eclampsia is highlighted by the study's results, with particular attention paid to the treatment of hypertension, proteinuria, and NT-proBNP levels [9]. By 12 weeks postpartum, most women had seen a positive resolution of these markers; however, a small proportion of women were still at risk for long-term problems, particularly cardiovascular health. One of the hallmarks of pre-eclampsia is hypertension, which must be resolved after delivery to lower the risk of cardiovascular disease in the long run [10]. One week after giving birth, 65% of the women in this study still had increased blood pressure; however, after a gradual improvement, 95% of the women's blood pressure levels returned to normal by the 12-week mark. These results are in line with earlier studies that demonstrate that although the majority of women who give birth recover from hypertension, some may need longer monitoring and care [11,12]. To avoid further cardiovascular

problems, it may be necessary to follow women for an extended period and possibly maintain antihypertensive medicine, as 5% of them still have hypertension [13].

Another sign of pre-eclampsia that suggests renal involvement is proteinuria. According to our findings, 90% of the participants' proteinuria had disappeared by 12 weeks, while 72% of them still experienced it one week after giving birth. Due to the possibility that the kidneys may require more time to heal from the inflammatory processes associated with pre-eclampsia, this pattern of delayed resolution of proteinuria is prevalent [14]. While most women's proteinuria goes away, 10% of individuals still had it 12 weeks later. This could indicate underlying renal injury or malfunction that has to be looked into further. It is advised that these women's kidney function be continuously monitored [15]. Recent years have seen an increase in interest in the function of NT-proBNP as a measure of cardiac stress in pre-eclampsia. Raised NT-proBNP levels are indicative of the condition's elevated blood pressure and accompanying fluid retention, which put stress on the heart. One week after giving birth, 78% of the patients in this study had increased NT-proBNP levels, which suggested severe cardiovascular stress [16]. 8% of women had elevated NT-proBNP levels at 12 weeks, even though levels had significantly fallen by 6 weeks. This suggests that these patients may be more vulnerable to long-term cardiovascular problems [17]. This is consistent with research that indicates women who suffer from pre-eclampsia are more likely to experience heart problems in the future. To lower the risk of heart disease in this

population, identifying patients with consistently elevated NT-proBNP levels may assist in direct more thorough follow-up and early therapies.

The results of this study have significant therapeutic ramifications for the postpartum care of women who have pre-eclampsia. A portion of patients, especially those with consistently increased NT-proBNP levels, are still at risk for long-term consequences even after the majority of women recover from hypertension and proteinuria within the first 12 weeks following birth [18]. Healthcare professionals should be informed of these dangers and think about keeping an eye on the kidney and cardiovascular systems for an extended period in women who have had pre-eclampsia. In this high-risk population, early intervention techniques like lifestyle changes, cardiovascular risk assessments, and, if required, pharmaceutical medication, may assist avert future health issues [19].

It is important to take into account the many limitations of this study when evaluating the findings. First, the findings might not be as applicable to larger groups due to the small sample size of 100 patients. Furthermore, the study was carried out at a single medical facility, which might not accurately represent the range of experiences in other contexts. Lastly, long-term consequences beyond the 12-week postpartum period were not evaluated because the study solely tracked the patients. To gain a deeper understanding of the long-term dangers associated with pre-eclampsia and the function of NT-proBNP in predicting cardiovascular outcomes, larger population studies with longer follow-up periods are required [20].

Conclusion

According to this study, after 12 weeks of giving birth, the majority of women with pre-eclampsia have a resolution of their hypertension, proteinuria, and NT-proBNP levels. A tiny percentage of women, meanwhile, still show indications of cardiovascular stress and might be vulnerable to long-term issues. These results highlight the significance of ongoing postpartum monitoring for pre-eclamptic women, especially for those with higher NT-proBNP levels, proteinuria, or unresolved hypertension. To better understand the long-term cardiovascular outcomes in this population and to create plans for early intervention and preventing future health hazards, more study is required.

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